

Beyond the Permafrost:

Excavated Tombs of Eastern Siberia

Archaeological data from the French-Sakha missions

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This catalog illustrates the comprehensive nature of the 114 tombs corresponding to the 124 individuals analyzed in paleogenomic research in the article «An Ancient DNA Perspective on the Russian Conquest of Yakutia.» Of these 124 individuals, 122—dated to the 15th–19th centuries—were excavated in Yakutia (Sakha Republic, Russian Federation) by a Franco-Yakut team between 2004 and 2018, following two years of surveys conducted in 2002 and 2003 and an additional year of research in southern Yakutia in 2019. One burial, Mokp or Pokrovsk Grave 6 (MOKP), dates to the Iron Age and was presented to us at the Pokrovsk Museum by Vassily Vassilievich. The final burial, known as Tungus, was excavated in Buryatia by Buryat colleagues contributing to the article; it is contemporaneous with some of the Yakut graves (see description).

Oyogosse Tumula 2 - (OYO2A, OYO2C)	108
Tchenkeloeil - (TCHEN)	109

Verkhoyansk

Byljasyk 3 - (BYLJ3)	111
Alyy - (ALYY)	112
Atyyr Meite 1 - (ATYY1)	114
Bakhtakh 3 - (BAKHT3)	115
Ieralaakh - (IERA_A, IERA_B)	116
Kureleekh 1 - (KUR1)	118
Kureleekh 2 - (KUR2)	120
Tysarastaakh 2 - (TYS2_A)	122
Buguyekh 3 - (BUGU3)	124
Kerdugen 1 - (KERDU)	125
Kouranakh - (KOURA)	126
Lepsei 1 - (LEPS1)	127
Lepsei 2 - (LEPS2)	128
Sordonokh - (SORD)	129
Byljasyk 2 - (BYLJ2)	131
Khoumakhtaakh - (KHOUM)	132
Kuskhegir 2 - (KUSKG2)	133

Lepsei 3 - (LEPS3)	134
Myran 1 - (MYRAN)	135
Ous Sire 1 - (OUS1)	136

Indigirka

Ebuguey 1 - (EBU1)	138
Ebuguey 2 - (EBU2)	139
Sobolokh 1 - (SOB1)	140
Balagannakh 2 - (BALA2)	142
Balagannakh 3 - (BALA3)	143
Omouk 1 - (OMK1)	144
Omouk 3 - (OMK3)	146
Pokos (POK1)	147
Sobolokh 2 - (SOB2)	148
Tomtor 2 - (TOMT2)	149
Touora Urekh - (TOUO2, TOUO3)	150

Buryatia

Tungus (Buryatia)	151
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Central Yakutia

Topographical relationships among buried individuals who are related and spatially close

These two photographic plates (the first from the At Daban site, the second from the Oulak site) examine the topographical relationships among related individuals buried in close proximity in the two burial sites in Central Yakutia. The At Daban site is located on a Quaternary terrace overlooking the Lena River, whereas the Oulak site is at the foot of this terrace. At both sites, the graves of related individuals are positioned near one another, and we present an analysis of these spatial relationships. In the case of At Daban, our study is enriched by historical records that indicate the burials belong to members of the same clan.

In some instances, related individuals were interred within the same grave, which we describe in detail in the corresponding tomb descriptions. However, related individuals were buried several dozen kilometers apart in other cases, suggesting no systematic intent to cluster related individuals within the same burial area.

Name: Mokp or Pokrovsk grave 6 - (MOKP)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Khangalassky)

GPS: 61.482102°N 129.151798°E

Period: Iron Age

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): harpoon, heads, elements of an armor made of reindeer bone, flint arrowhead, iron arrowhead, punch made of vestigial horse metatarsal.

Individual: male, adult.

Shaman status: no.

Name: At Daban 0 - (AD0)

Localisation: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Khangalassky)

GPS: 61.654419°N 129.262397°E

Period: anterior to 1700 AD

Chest or coffin: gutted trunk.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): bow, quiver with arrows (7), sword, birch pot.

Individual: Immature (boy), between 9 and 14 years old.

No clothing was found during the excavation.

Goods associated with the individual: earring (metal), sun disc, torque.

Shaman status: no.

Wealth level: 1 (torque)

A torque and metal earrings

Name: At Daban 11 - (AD11)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Khangalassky)

GPS: 61.651679°N 129.255702°E

Period: ~1,500 - 1,689 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, squared half-trunk coffin (external), tree trunk coffin (internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): sword, wooden pot with animal offerings, birch bark bag with animal offering (bovid), knife, iron needle.

Individual: Male, between 40 and 50 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations.

On the head: nothing.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): leather coat.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts and thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: boots.

Goods associated with the individual: nothing.

Shaman status: no.

A sword

A knife in its sheath

A wooden pot, with its decorated wall and its bottom

Name: Atlasovka - (ATLS)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Iakoutsk)

GPS: 62.003889°N 129.639444 °E

Period: ~1,500 - 1,689 CE

Chest or coffin: tree trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): bits, iron scissors, Mongolian knife, stirrups.

Individual: Female, 30-40 years old.

Remains of clothing were found during the excavation, but their nature could not be determined.

Goods associated with the individual: earrings.

During agricultural activities, archaeologists inadvertently unearthed a tomb 10 kilometers south of Yakutsk on a Quaternary terrace of the Lena River. What distinguishes this burial site is its occupant—a woman—which is unprecedented for the period in question. Notably, on the remains of her skull is the upper part of a hat, secured by a helical copper ornament designed to hold feathers. Archaeologists identified similar hemispherical-topped headdresses in the archaeological record between Lake Baikal and the mountains bordering Mongolia and China. Yakut oral traditions recount that, historically, between Yakutsk and Pokrovsk—a location congruent with the tomb's discovery—resided a tribe known as the Urankhai, of Mongolian origin. Presently, the name is associated with specific ethnic groups situated between Kazakhstan, Altai, and Siberia.

Shaman status: unsure.

Wealth level: 1 (decorated coat).

Decorations of an clothing and headdress

Name: Boyola 1 - (BOYO1)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Megino-Kangalassky)

GPS: 61.596156°N 131.064877°E

Period: ~1,500 - 1,689 CE

Chest or coffin: squared half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): saddle, stirrup, bow, long sword, quiver and arrows (7), turnbuckle, belt, knife and scabbard, food offering (horse), pouch.

Individual: Male, 30-40 years old.

Only a few items of clothing were found during the excavation.

On the head: ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): clothing (undefined).

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts.

On the feet: nothing.

Shaman status: yes (level 1: planted birch).

A traditional wooden saddle, placed under the head

A bow in its case and arrows in a quiver

Name: Djoussoulen - (DJOU)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Tchuraptcha).

GPS: 62.061679°N 132.668637°E

Period: ~1,500 - 1,689 CE

Chest or coffin: squared half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): saddle, bits, harness buckles, rug (Yakute-Bouryat weaving technique), knife, quiver and arrows (6), iron cauldron, bow, sword.

Individual: Male, adult.

Fragments of clothing were found during the excavation, but the advanced state of decay made it impossible to identify or describe them. The few protected remains are in the pelvis area.

On the head: sable ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): coat, fur clothing, beaded belt.

Goods associated with the individual: sun disk, earrings.

Shaman status: unsure (level 1: planted birch).

Wealth level: 1 (belt with pearls).

A sword

A sun disk and decorations of a belt

Name: Koudouk 4 - (KOUD4)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Khangalassky)

GPS: 61.635375°N 129.261208°E

Period: ~1,500 - 1,689 CE

Chest or coffin: squared half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): saddle, bow, arrowheads (bone and iron).

Individual: Male, adult.

Shaman status: no.

Name: Kyrdjakhas Taala 3 - (KYRDJ3)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Namsky)

GPS: 63.108110°N 129.528018°E

Period: ~1,500 - 1,689 CE

Chest or coffin: wooden logs coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): ivory fastener, food offering (bovid), leather bag, leather and wooden container, knife and case.

Individual: Male, 35-45 years old.

We found no clothing items except fragments of an under-head cushion made of sable fur.

Shaman status: no.

An ivory fastener

Name: Lampa 1 - (LAMP1)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Megino-Kangalassky)

GPS: 61.606988°N 131.131674°E

Period: ~1,500 - 1,689 CE

Chest or coffin: wooden logs coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): birch bark container, food offering (foal), knife (poorly preserved), belt buckle.

Individual: Male, adult.

We do not find traces of clothing at the excavation.

Shaman status: yes (level 1: planted birch).

A birch bark container

Name: Nelegher 1 - (NELE)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Tattinsky)

GPS: 62.620817°N 132.861317°E

Period: ~1,500 - 1,689 CE

Chest or coffin: wooden logs coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): food offering (horse), wooden spoon, wooden palette, birch bowls (2), knife, small sword.

Individual: Male, 50-60 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations. He is covered with a hare hide blanket and rests on a horsehide blanket.

On the head: traditional Yakut ushanka with horns.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): hide coat, sable shirt.

On the hands: mittens.

On the lower limbs: shorts, hide thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: boots.

Shaman status: no.

Bowls (in wood, in birch), a knife in its sheath, a wooden spoon, and a broken sword

Reconstructions of Nelegher man's clothing

Name: Ortodoidou 1 - (ODO1)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Khangalassky)

GPS: 61.680093°N 129.365208°E

Period: ~1,500 - 1,689 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, half-trunk coffin (external), tree trunk coffin (internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): birch bark pot.

Individual: Male, 40-50 years old.

At the excavation, only were preserved a few fragments of boots made of smoked leather.

Shaman status: no.

Birch bark pot

Name: Oulakh 2 - (OUL2)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Khangalassky)

GPS: 61.636014°N 129.345985°E

Period: ~1,500 - 1,689 CE

Chest or coffin: medium wood board coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): harness buckles, long sword, birch bark pot.

Individual: Male, 40-50 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations.

On the head: ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): nothing.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts, horse thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: nothing.

Shaman status: yes (level 1: planted birch).

Harness buckles, long sword, birch bark pot

Name: Oulakhan Alas - (OULK)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Tattinsky)

GPS: 62.625950°N 132.815650°E

Period: ~1,500 - 1,689 CE

Chest or coffin: wooden logs coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): bow, quiver and arrows (7/8), short sword, food offering (horse), traditional Yakut saddle, stirrups, traditional Yakut tripod vase (choron), whip, leather bag (fire bag), knife, leather container.

Individual: Male, 30-50 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations.

On the head: leather headdress.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): hide and fur garment, belt.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts, thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: boots.

Shaman status: no.

A traditional Yakut tripod vase (choron), a wooden stirrup, fastener and leather boot

Name: Taraläi - (TARL)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Tchuraptcha)

GPS: 62.003167°N 132.624733°E

Period: anterior to 1,689 AD

Chest or coffin: medium wood board coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): wooden pick, food offerings (horse, duck), short sword, knife, bone comb.

Individual: Male, 50-60 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations. He rests on a horsehide blanket.

On the head: nothing.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): leather shirt, coat.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: nothing.

On the feet: hide boots.

Shaman status: yes (level 1: planted birch).

A wooden fastener

Name: Tokhoï 1 - (TOKH)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Khangalassky)

GPS: 61.672359°N 129.367781°E

Period: ~1,500 - 1,689 CE

Chest or coffin: no trunk, the individual remains on a birch bark blanket.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): saddle, long sword, snaffle bit, knife.

Individual: Male, elderly.

No item of clothing is preserved.

Shaman status: no.

A sword blade, snaffle bit and a fastener

Name: Tyyt Bappyt 1 - (TYYT)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Tchuraptcha)

GPS: 62.026983°N 132.672419°E

Period: ~1,500 - 1,689 CE

Chest or coffin: squared half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): saddle, harness (rings and buckles), stirrup, bow, quiver and arrows (7), traditional Yakut tripod vase (choron), tweezers, birch bark pot, knife and scabbard.

Individual: Male, 30-50 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations.

On the head: leather ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): hide coat.

On the hands: sable mittens.

On the lower limbs: shorts, hide thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: boots.

Shaman status: no.

A traditional Yakut tripod vase (choron), a metal fastener of quiver, a birch bark pot and a wooden saddle

Name: Utchugueï Urekh - (UTCHU)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Iakoutsk)

GPS: 61.949364°N 129.627998°E

Period: ~1,500 - 1,689 CE

Chest or coffin: no trunk, the individual rests on a covering of birch bark.

Associated goods: bone and wooden buttons, bags, beads, wooden spoons.

Individual: Female, elderly.

Shaman status: no.

A wooden spoon, bone and wooden buttons and beads

Name: Vladimirovka - (VLAD)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Iakoutsk)

GPS: 61.990144°N 129.504728°E

Period: ~1,500 - 1,689 CE

Chest or coffin: wooden logs coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): Parts of pendants, arrowheads, bone parts of bows, ribs, horse jaws.

Individual: Male, adult.

Shaman status: no.

Name: Arbre Chamanique (AC1) or Okhtoubout - (AC1 S2, S3, S4, S5)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Tchuraptcha)

GPS: 62.043979°N 132.686401°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: half-trunk chest.

Number of individuals: 5 (individual 1 AC-S1, is not considered in the analyzes)

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): wooden bowl between individual II and III, wooden saddle with bronze decoration, birch bowl with food offering, a birch bark pouch, folded boots, Russian cloth bag, horse ribs (11), axe, 2nd man's saddle, stirrup, snaffle bit and bridle, 3rd birch pack saddle, wooden bowl and spoon, 2nd bridle in leather bag, food offering.

Individual II (AC1S2): Female, 18 - 23 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations.

On the head: traditional ushanka (fur hat) with horns, horsehide shroud. Mask.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): coat decorated with fur and textile, apron.

On the hands: nothing.

On lower limbs: horsehide shorts.

On the feet: high boots.

Goods associated with the individual: leather barrette, torques (2), signet ring.

Shaman status: yes (level 1: planted birch).

Wealth level: 4 (coat decorated, 2 torques, headband-leather barrette)

Individual III (AC1S3): Female, 40 – 55 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations.

On the head: traditional ushanka (fur hat) with horns.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): leather cape, two lynx and leather coats, thin textile shirt.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts and stockings in foal hide.

On the feet: reindeer hide boots.

Goods associated with the individual: 3 earrings, a knife, and a silver signet ring with a Yakut design.

Shaman status: yes (level 1: planted birch).

Individual IV (AC1S4): Immature (boy), between 1 and 4 years old.

The preservation of the individual makes it impossible to specify the types of clothing worn; only a few strips of leather clothing remain.

Shaman status: unsure (level 1: planted birch).

Individual V (AC1S5): Immature (girl), about five years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations.

On the head: horsehide bag, hare hide ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): wrapped in a foal hide blanket or coat.

On the hands: nothing.

Shaman status: unsure (level 1: planted birch).

A leather bag with pearl decorations and metal patterns, horsehide mittens, a birch bark bowl, a decorated star birch bark pouch and an axe

This grave overlooks a vast alas (meadow area) in central Yakutia. Its massive superstructure, the foundations of which we have discovered, was burned down by communist youth in the 1920's. A few hundred meters away lies the grave of Okhtoubout 2 - related to a shamanic tree - whose wooden staff evokes a shaman of Buryat tradition. The grave consists of a massive wooden chest containing four individuals, against which officiants buried a younger child. It housed a grandmother, two adults—her son and daughter—and two children. Officiants buried the five subjects simultaneously with numerous offerings, making this grave one of the wealthiest excavated- in Yakutia for this period. Apart from conventional offerings, such as saddles referencing the deceased's journey to an "otherworld," there are unique items like a birch bark pouch which is a tuktuye in which people enclosed the spirits of those who died unnaturally, out of fear that their malevolent spirits (üeurs) might return. Yakuts people also applied this practice to the spirits of shamans who passed away following rituals (Melanie). The spirits were symbolized by everyday objects, in the case of the shamanic tree grave tuktuye, by a bone arrow straightener. On the tuktuye of the shamanic tree, officiants carved a sun, a shamanic sign. In a skin bag, we found all the elements of a bride's belt - worn by young girls or female shamans - ready to be assembled. The mother of the children wears a mask, unique among over 200 subjects excavated in Yakutia. Traditionally, shamans could wear masks, and Yakut oral literature also reports that some married women might wear masks to hide.

Reconstructions of woman AC1 S2's clothing

Wooden saddle, with metal decorations and iron stirrups

Name: At Daban 4 - (AD4)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Khangalassky)

GPS: 61.651750°N 129.256033°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, squared half-trunk coffin (external), tree trunk coffin (internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): saddle, birch bark pot, food offerings (dairy product, horse), bow, quiver with several arrows, long sword, knife holder.

Individual: Male, 20-30 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations. He rests on a blanket.

On the head: ushanka, sable boa.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): leather coat, textile shirt, belt with metal decoration.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: leather shorts, two pairs of leather and fur thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: leather boots.

Shaman status: no.

Wealth level: 1 (belt with metal decoration).

Iron harness buckles, iron stirrups and male belt with shell metal decorations

*Reconstructions of man AD4's clothing,
with his decorated leather quiver*

Name: At Daban 6 - (AD6)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Khangalassky)

GPS: 61.654364°N 129.262012°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, squared half-trunk coffin (external), tree trunk coffin (internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): saddle, stirrups, harness, cauldron (iron), birch pot, birch bark pot, horse offering (ribs), bronze bracelets (2), earrings (1) and signet rings (3), articulated snaffle bit, decorated net, knife.

Individual: Female, over 50 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations.

On the head: ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): nothing identifiable, a dress was laid over the body.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts.

On the feet: leather boots.

Goods associated with the individual: sun disk, earrings, torque, ring.

Shaman status: no.

Wealth level: 6 (decorated coat, torque, 2 bracelets, ring, enameled handle knife).

Female jewelry (torque, earrings, bracelets), sun disk, iron cauldron and snaffle bit

Reconstructions of women AD6's clothing, with cloisonné objects (knife handle and button)

Name: At Daban 7 - (AD7)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Khangalassky)

GPS: 61.658103°N 129.272752°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, half-trunk coffin (external), tree trunk coffin (internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): birch pot, food offerings (dairy, horse, meat), birch chopstick/cane, birch bark pot and bag, knife.

Individual: Male, very elderly.

We recovered clothes during the excavations.

On the head: fox fur ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): fur coat.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts, thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: nothing.

Shaman status: unsure (level 1: command stick).

A birch bark pot, and a birch bowl

Name: At Daban 8 - (AD8)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Khangalassky)

GPS: 60.654655°N 129.264719°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: medium wood board coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): nothing.

Individual: Female, 25-30 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations.

On the head: ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): apron, bride's belt.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts.

On the feet: nothing.

Goods associated with the individual: earrings (3).

Shaman status: yes (level 1: bride's belt).

A apron of bride's belt (beads and metal plaques), earrings and a metal decoration of clothing

Name: At Daban 10 - (AD10)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Khangalassky)

GPS: 61.651528°N 129.254400°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, squared half-trunk coffin (external), tree trunk coffin (internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): saddle, stirrups and harness buckles, axe, bronze and iron cauldron, wooden spoon, birch pot with dairy product, food offerings (horse and bovid), scraper.

Individual: Male (osteological sex), between 20 and 30 years old.

He rests on a horse fur blanket. We recovered clothes during the excavations.

On the head: traditional Yakut ushanka, fur shroud, sable-tailed boa.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): leather coat.

On the hands: very fine leather mittens.

On the lower limbs: leather shorts, thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: leather stockings, leather boots.

Goods associated with the individual: wooden knife holder.

Shaman status: no.

Wealth level: 3 (bronze cauldron, axe, horse comb).

A bronze cauldron with its iron handle, harness' buckles, an axe, a knife in its bronze decorations sheath and a saddle

Name: At Daban 12 - (AD12)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Khangalassky)

GPS: 61.651629°N 129.255519°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: medium wood board coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): sword, birch pot.

Individual: Male (osteological sex), young.

Rare fragments of clothing were found during the excavation.

On the head: textile shroud, silk headband.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): beaded belt, coat.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts.

On the feet: nothing.

Shaman status: no.

Wealth level: 1 (belt with pearls).

A sword and reconstruction of male decorated shorts

Name: At Daban 13 - (AD13)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Khangalassky)

GPS: 61.651208°N 129.253549°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: medium wood board coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): saddle, stirrups (2), harness buckle, bow, quiver and 7 arrows, bow binder, long sword, horse comb, snaffle bit, wooden pot, cauldron (bronze and iron), two spoons, braided cord, needle (ivory), knife, pipe (in the boot), food offering (horse).

Individual: Male, 40-50 years old.

Rare fragments of clothing were found during the excavation.

On the head: nothing.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): nothing.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: two pairs of socks, thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: boots.

Shaman status: no.

Wealth level: 2 (bronze cauldron, horse comb).

A bronze cauldron, with its iron handle, a wooden spoon, knife and pipe

Snaffle bit, iron stirrup, arrows in their leather quiver and its bone and iron fasteners, and a sword

Name: Bere 1 - (BERE)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Megino-Kangalassky).

GPS: 61.756122°N 130.820213°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: anthropomorphic squared half-trunk.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): food offerings (bovine, foal), saddle, complete harness (snaffle bit, bridle, stirrup, saddle pad), wooden cup, whip ("knout"), leather bag, pipe, knife (in its holder).

Individual: Female, over 50 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations. She rests on a fox fur coat.

On the head: ushanka (shroud), traditional Yakut ushanka with horns, squirrel fur boa.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): coat with eagle wing motif on back, 2nd coat, shirt.

On the hands: leather mittens.

On the lower limbs: shorts, vaginal swab, thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: socks, boots.

Goods associated with the individual: sun disk, earrings (4).

Shaman status: yes (level 1: planted birch).

Wealth level: 1 (decorated coat).

A saddle and its stirrups

Reconstructions of Bere tomb superstructure and coffin

Reconstructions of woman Bere's clothing, with its earrings, a pipe and harness' buckles

Name: Bittiki - (BITTI)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Namsky)

GPS: 62.689839°N 129.283499°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, squared half-trunk coffin (external), thin wood board coffin (internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): wooden bowl, ceramic, wooden box, food offering (dairy product), two wooden pots, wooden spoon, spoon, arrow (1), two bows (different sizes), knife

Individual: Immature, about 4 years old. We recovered clothes during the excavations. He is wrapped in a foal hide blanket.

On the head: fur shroud, ushanka, silk scarf.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): two coats.

On the hands: thin leather mittens.

On the lower limbs: shorts, stockings.

On the feet: boots.

Shaman status: no.

A wooden pot and spoon, a birch bowl and two bows of different sizes

Name: Boyola 2 - (BOYO2)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Megino-Kangalassky)

GPS: 61.596254°N 131.064300°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: squared half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): nothing.

Individual: Female, 20-30 years old.

A few items of clothing were found during the excavation.

On the head: traditional Yakut ushanka with horns.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): coat, shirt.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts, thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: boots.

Goods associated with the individual: earrings (2).

Shaman status: yes (level 1: bride's belt).

Wealth level: 1 (decorated coat).

Reconstructions of woman Boyola2's clothing, with its earrings and some Chinese and European coins decorating ushanka and short

Name: Eletcheï 2 - (ELET2)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Megino-Kangalassky)

GPS: 61.701264°N 131.314639°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: half-trunk coffin and thick wood board.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): knife holder, food offering (meat, horse), birch bark pot, spoon, birch bowl, wooden container, knife.

Individual: Immature (girl), 7-9 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations. She rests on a sable blanket.

On the head: ushanka (shroud), traditional Yakut ushanka, boa.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): sable coat, leather coat, beaded belt, shirt.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts, genital swab, thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: boots.

Goods associated with the individual: earrings (4), ring, torque.

Shaman status: yes (level 3: planted birch, contention, restraint).

Wealth level: 4 (torque, ring, belt with pearls, pearl embellished boots).

Reconstructions of young girl Eletcheï2' clothing, with its earrings and torque

A birch bark pot and its watercolor

Name: Iskra - (ISKRA)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Namsky)

GPS: 62.711509°N 129.302615°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: squared half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): wooden bowl, knife and scabbard (wood).

Individual: Male (osteological sex), 25-30 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations. He rests on a blanket.

On the head: fur shroud.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): fur coat, leather coat, belt with pendants.

On the hands: mittens.

On the lower limbs: shorts.

On the feet: nothing.

Shaman status: no.

A wooden bowl, a men's belt with bridal belt pendants repurposed as decorations, and a knife with its sheath

Name: Khorogor - (KHOR)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Iakoutsk)

GPS: 61.947561°N 129.565458°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: tree trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): pearl leather knife case.

Individual: Immature (girl), adolescent.

Shaman status: no.

Name: Koudouk 2 - (KOUD2)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Khangalassky)

GPS: 61.635144°N 129.259839°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: squared half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): birch bark pot with graffiti, ceramic fragments.

Individual: Female, adult.

Shaman status: no.

Ceramic fragment, birch bark pot and white beads

Name: Koudouk 5 - (KOUD5)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Khangalassky)

GPS: 61.635653°N 129.262106°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: squared half-trunk coffin.

Individual: Female, adult.

Goods associated with the Individual: torque, pendant with two horse heads, earrings.

Shaman status: no.

Wealth level: 1 (torque).

A torque, earrings and metal decorations of clothing

Name: Kous Tcharbyt - (KOUT)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Tattinsky)

GPS: 62.625683°N 132.856167°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, squared half-trunk coffin (external), tree trunk coffin (internal), compartment for goods (between external and internal coffin).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): wooden pot, iron cauldron, birch bowl, spoon, remnants of backpack, leather gourd, knife, food offering (horse), traditional Yakut monopod vase (choron) with diaru products, wooden vase, birch bowl, leather bag, axe, whip/riding crop (knout), quiver and arrows (6), bow, long sword.

Individual: Male, 40-60 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations. He rests on a blanket.

On the head: fur ushanka, shroud.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): foal hide coat, leather shirt, sable waistcoat, belt.

On the hands: mittens.

On the lower limbs: shorts, two pairs of thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: hide socks, leather boots.

Shaman status: yes (level 1: planted birch).

Wealth level: 2 (axe, belt with metal decorations).

Reconstruction of a man's garment with his belt where the knout and the sheath of his knife are suspended.

A wooden spoon and decorated pot

Wooden frame of a backpack, a birch bowl, a traditional Yakut monopod vase (choron), an iron cauldron and an axe

Name: Kyrджакhas Taala 1 - (KYRDJ1)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Namsky)

GPS: 63.108667°N 129.527867°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): food offerings (horse, dairy products), saddle, stirrup, harness buckle, knife, birch bowl, spoon (2), ceramic pot.

Individual: Female, 30-40 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations. She is covered with horse fur and rests on horse fur.

On the head: shroud (traditional Yakut ushanka with horns), sable boa.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): textile coat, textile shirt.

On the hands: mittens.

On the lower limbs: thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: boots.

Goods associated with the individual: earrings (4), signet rings with Yakut coat of arms, torque.

Shaman status: no.

Wealth level: 1 (torque).

A knife, iron stirrup and harness' buckle

A birch bowl, wooden spoons, jewelry (earrings, torque and signet ring) and ceramic fragments

Name: Kyys Ounouoga 1 - (KYYS)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Tchuraptcha)

GPS: 62.036833°N 132.686550°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: squared half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): birch pot, wooden bowl, food offerings (horse, dairy products).

Individual: Female, 20-25 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations.

On the head: silk ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): textile coat, bride's belt.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: boots.

Goods associated with the individual: earring.

Shaman status: yes (level 5: command stick, planted birch, contention, restraint).

Wealth level: 1 (decorated coat).

Reconstruction of woman Kyys' clothing and its earrings

Reconstruction of woman Kyys' clothing with its apron and bride belt. A birch bowl and wooden decorated pot

Name: Molor 2 - (MOL2)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Namsky)

GPS: 62.575970°N 128.849155°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: medium wood board coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): bow, wooden pot, wooden spoon, quiver and arrows (7), traditional Evenk weapon, bow stringer, knife and sheath.

Individual: Male (osteological sex), about 25 years old.

Only the remains of a fur coat and a belt buckle were found at the time of the excavation.

Shaman status: no.

A knife and its sheath, iron buckle and fragments of wooden pot

Blade of a traditional Evenk weapon, bone extremities of a bow, iron fastener and different types of arrows

Name: Odjuluun 2 - (ODJU2)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Charpchinsky)

GPS: 61.870623°N 132.412986°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): leather container, wooden pot, food offering (horse), birch box, pipe, jewellery box (2 pairs of earrings, 2 bracelets, 2 leather purses)

Individual: Female, 30-35 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations. She rests on a birch blanket. A hare hide blanket is placed over the body.

On the head: fur ushanka, fur shroud.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): foal hide coat, cotton shirt.

On the hands: sable mittens.

On the lower limbs: deer shorts, thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: hide boots.

Goods associated with the individual: sun disk, earrings, signet rings (2).

Shaman status: yes (level 2: planted birch, contention).

Wealth level: 3 (decorated coat, 2 bracelets).

A wooden bowl and pipe

A signet ring, bracelets and earrings

Name: Okhtoubout 2 - (OKHT2)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Tchuraptcha)

GPS: 62.041200°N 132.697167°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): food offering (foal), knife, birch bark pot, a wooden staff like those of shamans of the Buryat tradition ; leather bag.

Individual: Female, elderly.

We recovered clothes during the excavations.

On the head: nothing.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): deer coat.

On the hands: leather mittens.

On the lower limbs: shorts, sable thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: boots.

Goods associated with the individual: earring (1).

Shaman status: yes (level 2: command stick, planted birch).

A wooden walking staff, decorations of clothing and birch bark pot

Name: Oktiom 1 - (OKT1_S1, S2, S4, S5)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Khangalassky)

GPS: 61.692844°N 129.394184°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: great thin wood board coffin.

Individual number: 4 (7 in total).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest):

A quiver with its 10 arrows, blade of a sword, rectangular birch box, ceramic pot, 4 birch bark pots, wooden pot, wooden spoon, two knives in its sheath and torque.

Individual 1 (Oktiom1Sujet1): Male, 30-35 years old. The clothes are poorly preserved, although some indications have been found.

On the head: traditional Yakut ushanka with horns.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): horse fur coat, sable and hare fur coat, some pearls decorated one of the coats.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: fur thigh-high leg warmers

On the feet: nothing.

Goods associated with the individual: sun disk.

Shaman status: unsure (level 1: engraving coffin).

Wealth level: 1 (decorated coat).

Individual 2 (Oktiom1Sujet2): Immature (girl), 2-3 years old.

We discovered, poorly preserved, only some parts of clothes.

On the head: ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): horse fur coat, 2nd coat.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: nothing;

On the feet: nothing.

Goods associated with the individual: torque.

Shaman status: no.

Wealth level: 2 (decorated coat, torque).

Individual 4 (Oktiom1Sujet4): Immature (boy), 2-3 years old.

We discovered, poorly preserved, only some parts of clothes.

On the head: nothing.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): sable fur coat. On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: nothing.

On the feet: nothing.

Goods associated with the individual: nothing.

Shaman status: no.

Individual 5 (Oktiom1Sujet5): Immature (boy), about 12 years old.

The clothes are poorly preserved, although some indications have been found.

On the head: nothing.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): fur coat.
 On the hands: nothing.
 On the lower limbs: sable shorts, horse thigh-high leg warmers.
 On the feet: nothing.

Goods associated with the individual: nothing.

Shaman status: no.

The order of the deposits is particular, and the officiants deliberately staged them. The adult was placed at the center of the western half with a child on each side, including the third subject (aged 5 to 6 years) on the right, lying on his stomach, appearing to an external observer as though he was holding the adult's hand. Officiants placed a small child between the adult and the child to his left. Then, three children were laid in the eastern part, facing the first three, with the oldest placed in a flexed position on the adult's lower limbs and a child on either side. We dated the grave by C14 to the 17th century. The associated grave goods are typical of a hunter/warrior for the adult, and officiants placed pots in the corner of the eastern part before depositing the three children. One of these vessels, a ceramic vase, is attributed to the Kulun-Atakh culture, which archaeologists date from the 14th to the 17th century in central Yakutia.

Knife in its sheath, arrows, blade of a sword, torque and birch bark pot and its wooden spoon

Name: Ortodoidou 3 - (ODO3)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Khangalassky)

GPS: 61.680242°N 129.367165°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: tree trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): wooden pot, spoon, food offering (horse), knife, pearls.

Individual: Male, over 50 years old.

We found only a few fragments of clothes.

On the head: nothing.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): nothing.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts, horse fur thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: boots.

Shaman status: no.

Knife, blue bead and belt buckle

Name: Oulakh 4 - (OULA)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Khangalassky)

GPS: 61.636294°N 129.346614°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: squared half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): saddle, stirrups, knife, bow, quiver and arrows (9), whip (knout), food offering.

Individual: Male, 30-40 years old.

The only clothing evidence is a bronze ring suggesting the wearing of shorts.

Shaman status: no.

Fragments of harness buckle, stirrup and blade of knife, a bow and arrows in a leather quiver

Name: Oulakh 5 - (OUL5)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Khangalassky)

GPS: 61.636293°N 129.346707°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: thin wood board coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): bow, quiver and arrows (6), long sword, birchbark pot, knife, quiver clasp or bow-stringer, pearls.

Individual: Male, 20-30 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations.

On the head: ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): fur coat.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: nothing.

On the feet: nothing.

Shaman status: no.

A birch bark pot, iron fastener, different types of arrows (bone or iron extremities), bow and sword

Name: Rassoloda - (RASS)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Megino-Kangalassky)

GPS: 61.680558°N 129.627225°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: unknown.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): fragment of ceramic pot, knife, bronze buckle from shorts.

Individual: Female, adult.

Goods associated with the individual: torque, earrings.

Shaman status: no.

Wealth level: 1 (torque).

Name: Sette Toumoul - (SETTE)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Tattinsky)

GPS: 62.296750°N 132.818950°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): birch pot (flat), food offerings, wooden container, fire bag, knife, leather bag with beads.

Individual: Male, about 40 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations. He rests on a hare blanket.

On the head: fur ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): leather clothing, shirt, belt.

On the hands: leather mittens.

On the lower limbs: sable shorts, two pairs of thigh-high leg warmers (leather and hide).

On the feet: socks, leather boots.

Shaman status: no.

Belt buckle, knife and its sheath and leather bag decoration

Name: Sola 2 - (SOLA2)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Megino-Kangalassky)

GPS: 61.758008°N 130.961781°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: squared half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): harness, food offering (horse), small wooden pot, wooden dish, wooden pot, quiver and arrows, bow, turnbuckle, knife case, lighter, pliers, pipe.

Individual: Male, 30-50 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations.

On the head: nothing.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): horse coat, belt.

On the hands: hare fur mittens.

On the lower limbs: hare hide thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: two pairs of socks (fur and hide), leather boots.

Shaman status: no.

Wealth level: 1 (horse comb).

Wooden containers and a pipe

A bow in its scabbard, a leather quiver, a horse comb scraper, a knife scabbard, an iron fastener, a horse curb chain and a harness buckle

Name: Tchotchour 1 - (TCHO1)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Khangalassky)

GPS: 62.001081°N 129.596969°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: tree trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): 2 wooden bowls, food offering (foal).

Individual: Female, 40-50 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations.

On the head: traditional Yakut leather ushanka with horns

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): leather coat.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts, thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: boots.

Goods associated with the individual: earrings.

Shaman status: no.

Name: Urun Myran 1 - (URUN1)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Menigho Khangalass)

GPS: 61.769925°N 130.890952°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: squared half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): birch pot, food offerings (foal, dairy product), wooden pot, ceramic fragments, bow, long sword, quiver and arrows (7), turnbuckle, birch bark pot, knife.

Individual: Male, adult.

We recovered clothes during the excavations.

On the head: fur shroud, fur ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): two leather coats, fur shirt.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: fur shorts, thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: boots.

Shaman status: yes (level 1: planted birch).

Birch pot, wooden pot, long sword, bow, quiver and seven arrows

Name: At Byran 7 - (AB7)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Khangalassky)

GPS: 61.651514°N 129.255225°E

Period: 1,750-1800 AD

Chest or coffin: squared half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): food offering, birch pot, pipe.

Individual: Female, adult.

Goods associated with the individual: earrings.

Shaman status: no.

Name: At Daban 9 - (AD9)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Khangalassky)

GPS: 61.654889°N 129.263075°E

Period: 1,750 - 1,800 CE

Chest or coffin: squared half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): food offering in leather bag (horse), pearls.

Individual: Female, 45-50 years old.

We found remains of clothing, but we could not determine their nature.

Goods associated with the individual: earrings (2).

Shaman status: no.

Name: Batta Tcharana - (BATA)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Tattinsky).

GPS: 62.276767°N 132.856050°E

Period: 1,750 - 1,800 CE

Chest or coffin: half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): traditional Yakut saddle, stirrups, food offerings (horse, meat), wooden pot, knife.

Individual: Male, over 50 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavation.

On the head: shroud, two ushanka, textile scarf.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): fur coat, daba shirt, horsehide waistcoat.

On the hands: mittens.

On the lower limbs: shorts, thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: boots.

Shaman status: unsure, (level 1: contention).

A wooden bowl, a folded blade knife and a wooden saddle

Name: Bouogaryma 1 - (BOUO1)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Tattinsky)

GPS: 62.285800°N 133.834583°E

Period: 1,750 - 1,800 CE

Chest or coffin: anthropomorphic (hollow for shoulders) half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): stirrups (2), buckle, bow, leather belt, arrows (3), knife and scabbard.

Individual: Male in prone position (rare), about 40 years old (30-50 years old). We recovered clothes during the excavations. He rests on a white hare hide blanket.

On the head: scarf.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): leather garment (indefinite), belt.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts, thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: socks, thigh-high boots.

Shaman status: no.

Buckle, knife, stirrups, bow and arrows

Name: Bouogaryma 2 - (BOUO2)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Tattinsky)

GPS: 62.285843°N 132.833755°E

Period: 1,750 - 1,800 CE

Chest or coffin: anthropomorphic (hollow for shoulders) half-trunk coffin.
Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): knife, hide bag, wooden bowl, braided rope.

Individual: Female, elderly.

We recovered clothes during the excavations. She rests on an animal hide blanket.

On the head: ushanka (textile and fur), leather shroud.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): coat, shirt.

On the hands: textile mittens.

On the lower limbs: shorts, thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: socks, boots.

Goods associated with the individual: earrings (4).

Shaman status: no.

Wooden bowl, earrings

Name: Eletcheï 1 - (ELET1)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Megino-Kangalassky)

GPS: 61.698311°N 131.214178°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, half-rounders coffin (external), anthropomorphic squared half-trunk coffin (internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): knife and case, spare pair of boots, harness and buckle, travel bag, food offering (meat, horse, dairy), thermos flask, birch bowl, wooden pot, fly swatter, leather container, toiletries: comb, thread, thimble; saddlebags (2), wooden container (2), leather bag, chamois bag, saddle, stirrups, bridle, whip (knout), pipe (brass stove).

Individual: Female, about 40 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations. She rests on a blanket (foal).

On the head: ushanka (shroud), 1st traditional Yakut ushanka with horns, 2nd ushanka, boa.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): 1st coat, 2nd coat, dress, shirt, beaded belt.

On the hands: mittens.

On the lower limbs: beaded shorts, two pairs of thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: 3 pairs of boots.

Goods associated with the individual: earrings (4), signet rings (2).

Shaman status: yes (level 1: planted birch).

Wealth level: 4 (2 decorated coats, red wool, belt with pearls).

Decorated front of the saddle

Reconstructions of woman Eletchei' clothing, with a comb in a wooden box, birch bowl, pipe, stirrup and decorated birch pot (and its watercolor)

Name: Eletcheï 3 - (ELET3)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Menigho-Khangalass)

GPS: 61.700193°N 131.316031°E

Period: 1,750 - 1,800 CE

Chest or coffin: squared half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): nothing.

Individual: Male, 30-50 years old.

The only clothing evidence is an iron belt buckle and remnants of leather around the hips.

Shaman status: no.

Iron belt buckle

Name: Koudouk 3 - (KOUD3)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Khan-galassky)

GPS: 61.633675°N 129.254400°E

Period: 1,750 - 1,800 CE

Chest or coffin: squared half-trunk coffin

Individual: Female, adult.

Goods associated with the Individual: earrings with pendant with two horse heads.

Shaman status: no.

Name: Lampa 2 - (LAMP2)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Megino-Kangalassky)

GPS: 61.613493°N 131.060660°E

Period: 1,750 - 1,800 CE

Chest or coffin: anthropomorphic half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): knife and scabbard, pipe, smoking kit (tobacco pouch, lighter).

Individual: Male (osteological sex), adult.

We recovered clothes during the excavations. He rests on an animal hide blanket.

On the head: textile shroud, ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): leather coat, leather belt.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: hide thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: leather boots.

Shaman statuts: yes (level 4: planted birch, contention, restraint, shroud on face).

A pipe along the leg and a knife with a bent blade

Name: Magan - (MAGAN)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Iakoutsk)

GPS: 61.094917°N 129.701644°E

Period: 1,750 - 1,800 CE

Chest or coffin: squared half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): food offering, lighter, bark knife case, two Mossin rifle cases, birch pot.

Individual: Male, adult.

Shaman status: no.

Name: Ortodoidou 2 - (ODO2)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Khangalassky)

GPS: 61.680410°N 129.366863°E

Period: 1,750 - 1,800 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, squared half-trunk coffin (external), tree trunk coffin (internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): nothing.

Individual: Female, 30-40 years old.

Only a few fragments of silk, which may correspond to a dress, and fragments of leather boots were preserved.

Shaman status: no.

Wealth level: 1 (silk dress).

Name: Tchapaev 1 - (TCHAP1_nord, sud)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Khangalassky)

GPS: 61.668053°N 129.359741°E

Period: 1,750 - 1,800 CE

Chest or coffin: two thin wood board coffins joined
Number of individuals: 2 (and a newborn -white circle).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): nothing.

Individual 1 north: Female (osteological sex), 20-23 years old. No clothing is preserved.

Goods associated with the individual: knife, wooden pot, food offering (dairy products).

Shaman status: no.

Individual 1 South: Female (osteological sex), 23-25 years old.

Few items of clothing have been preserved. Two buttons have been found and may belong to a coat and a buckle may belong to shorts and thigh-high leg warmers.

Shaman status: no.

Buttons and decorative elements of clothing

Name: Tottouk 1 - (TOTTK)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Namsky)

GPS: 62.698898°N 129.262677°E

Period: 1,750 - 1,800 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, half-trunk coffin (external), tree trunk coffin (internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): stirrups (2), harness, wooden pot, leather bag, food offering (horse), wooden skewer, walking stick, wooden bowl, spoon, traditional non-Yakut knife, whisk-scraper, long sword, wooden ties.

Individual: Male, over 60 years old.

Despite the poor preservation of the clothes, some could be identified. He rests on a horsehide blanket.

On the head: nothing.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): fur coat, leather belt with metal decorations.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: leather shorts.

On the feet: nothing.

Shaman status: no.

Wealth level: 2 (horse comb, belt with metal decorations).

An extremity of whisk-scraper, iron buckle, wooden pot, stirrups, decorated male belt

*Wooden bowl and spoon,
knife fragments, whisk-scraper,
wooden sticks for
closing a bag and a bow*

Name: Us Sergue 1 - (USS1)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Khangalassky)

GPS: 61.634401°N 129.314629°E

Period: 1,750 - 1,800 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, half-rounders coffin (external), tree trunk coffin (internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): a space is left for depositing goods: food offerings (horse, dairy product), leather bag, two wooden pots, small wooden bowl, personal belongings box, traditional Yakut monopod vase (choron), needles (bronze), hook, comb, knife and sheath, fly whisk, saddle, harness, snaffle bit, stirrup, bell, sharpener.

Individual: Female, 30-40 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations. She rests on a horse blanket. A scarlet dress is pulled below her head.

On the head: shroud (silk scarf), fur scarf, traditional Yakut ushanka, sable boa.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): fur coat, textile (dabba) coat, textile belt, leather belt.

On the hands: textile mittens.

On the lower limbs: leather thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: leather socks, leather boots.

Goods associated with the individual: bronze sun disk, earrings (4), torque (1), leather headband with 38 coins, a bride's belt.

Shaman status: yes (level 3: bride's belt, small bell, shroud on face).

Wealth level: 6 (red wool, silk inserts coat, leather headband, fly whisk, personal belongings box, bronze bell).

Traditional Yakut ushanka with bronze sun disk

This grave of a woman aged between 30 and 40 years is in the alluvial plain of the Lena River, a few kilometers from At Daban, on a terrain knoll. A few meters from it, a pit contains three horses, one with decorations matching the woman's dress. The local name of the site is "Us Sergue," which means in Yakut "the three posts for tying horses," and the memory of this woman buried with three horses must have persisted for a long time. Moreover, a few meters from her grave is a later Christian cemetery. Therefore, the grave was a focal point for developing a subsequent cemetery, which signifies a highly respected individual in Yakutia. Despite its late dating during the Christianization of Yakutia, this grave shows no signs of Christianization.

On the contrary, it exhibits many traditional features, including two chests containing a huge hollowed trunk holding a wealthy woman's remains. Indeed, in addition to the imposing grave, there is a significant amount of furnishings placed in the chest, several coats richly decorated, and she wore a red woolen dress made from imported blankets, likely English, found only among a few exceptional female individuals. She wears a bride's belt characteristic of shaman women, and near her, there are remains of ties; she was initially bound, like the shaman Kyys.

Reconstructions of woman USS1' clothing. Saddle with metal stirrups, harness, bell and knife in its sheath

Reconstructions of woman USS1' clothing. A traditional Yakut monopod vase (choron), leather headband with coins, comb, torque, and pendants of bride's belt

Name: Ken Ebé 3 - (KEB3)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Tattinsky)

GPS: 62.313646°N 133.508414°E

Period: 1,800 - 1,922 CE

Chest or coffin: thin wood board coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): nothing.

Individual: Immature, about 8 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations. He/She is completely covered in a cotton shroud.

On the head: shroud, scarf.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): leather coat, cotton shirt.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts, thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: boots.

Goods associated with the individual: Christian cross.

Shaman status: no.

Name: Ken Ebé 8 - (KEB8)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Tattinsky)

GPS: 62.319950°N 133.506717°E

Period: 1,800 - 1,922 CE

Chest or coffin: medium wood board coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): nothing.

Individual: Female, very elderly.

During the excavation, we discovered clothes that were poorly preserved. A horsehide pillow is placed under the head.

On the head: nothing.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): textile tunic, leather belt.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts.

On the feet: boots.

Goods associated with the individual: Christian cross.

Shaman status: no.

Name: Koudouk 1 - (KOUD)

Localisation: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Khangalassky)

GPS: 61.632978°N 129.293983°E

Period: 1,800 - 1,922 CE

Chest or coffin: squared half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): nothing.

Individual: Female, over 60 years old.

During the excavation, we discovered clothes that were poorly preserved.

On the head: fur ushanka, silk scarf.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): remains of coat buckles.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: remnants of shorts buckles and traces of oxidation on the buckles of the thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: boots, leather socks.

Goods associated with the individual: earrings (1).

Shaman status: no.

Name: Otchugouï - (OTCH)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Megino-Kangalassky)

GPS: 67.709613°N 131.031240°E

Period: 1,800 - 1,922 CE

Chest or coffin: anthropomorphic half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): nothing.

Individual: Female, 30-35 years old.

During the excavation, we recovered clothes.

On the head: ushanka (fur, silk and textile), squirrel fur boa.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): chamois coat, unidentified clothing.

On the hands: mittens (fur, silk, and textile).

On the lower limbs: nothing.

On the feet: boots.

Goods associated with the individual: Christian cross.

Shaman status: unsure (level 1: contention).

Name: Toutekh 1 - (TOUTK)

Location: Central Yakutia (Uluus: Menigho Khangalass)

GPS: 61.735021°N 130.891383°E

Period: 1,800 - 1,922 CE

Chest or coffin: squared half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): knife.

Individual: Male, elderly.

During the excavation, we recovered clothes.

On the head: Women's silk ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): leather coat

On the hands: mittens.

On the lower limbs: shorts, thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: fur boots.

Goods associated with the individual: Christian cross, signet ring (1).

Shaman status: no.

Signet ring

Vilyuy

Name: Oyogosse Tumula 1 - (OYO1)

Location: Vilyuy (Uluus: Nurbinsky)

GPS: 63.586716°N 119.130323°E

Period: ~1,500 - 1,689 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, wooden logs coffin (external), tree trunk coffin (internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): food offering (foal), birch pot, wooden bowl.

Individual: Male, very elderly.

During the excavation, we recovered clothes.

On the head: ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): belt with metal decorations.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts, thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: nothing.

Shaman status: no.

Wealth level: 1 (belt with metal decorations).

Name: Tympy 1 - (TYMP1)

Location: Vilyuy (Uluus: Nurbinsky)

GPS: 63.560444°N 119.118194°E

Period: ~1,500 - 1,689 CE

Chest or coffin: wooden logs coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): birch pot.

Individual: Male, elderly with extensive bone trauma (peri-mortem).

Clothes are not preserved.

Shaman status: no.

Name: Boulgounniakh 1 - (BOULG1)

Location: Vilyuy (Uluus: Suntarsky)

GPS: 61.963500°N 117.137633°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: tree trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): birch pots (2), food offerings (horse, meat), harness, stirrup, buckles (3), iron cauldron, burl pot, bow, long sword, quiver and arrows (7), bow stringer, wooden whip (knout), axe (Russian form), saddle, knife.

Individual: Male, 40-60 years old.

During the excavation, we recovered clothes.

On the head: shroud, ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): coat, silk shirt (Russian inspiration), belt.

On the hands: the sleeve is sewn onto the hand.

On the lower limbs: two pairs of pants (one inside out), fur stockings.

On the feet: boots.

Goods associated with the individual: sun disk, signet rings (2).

Shaman status: yes (level 1: restraint).

Wealth level: 3 (silk shirt, axe, knife with bronze decoration handle).

Reconstruction of the BOULG1 man's clothing and signet rings. Signet rings, bone fastener, cauldron, knife, axe, buckle and iron stirrup

Name: Boulgounniakh 2 - (BOULG2)

Location: Vilyuy (Uluus: Suntarsky)

GPS: 61.963650°N 117.135852°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, half-trunk coffin (external), tree trunk coffin (internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): knife and pearl-embellished sheath, wooden pot, food offering (dairy product), whip (knout), 2 birch containers, bronze cauldron, spoon, trident-shaped object, saddle, stirrups, bit, buckles and leather straps.

Individual: Female, about 30 years old.

During the excavation, we recovered clothes. She rests on a reindeer hide blanket.

On the head: ushanka (shroud), traditional Yakut ushanka with horns, sable boa.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): fox fur coat, leather coat, textile clothing.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts, "cache-sexe", two pairs of thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: boots.

Goods associated with the individual: sun disk, torque, earrings (4), 5 rings.

Her grave was locally known as that of a shaman, and it is associated with a bride's belt.

Shaman status: yes (level 3: planted birch, restraint, bride's belt).

Wealth level: 9 (bronze cauldron, decorated coat, torque, 5 rings, pearl-embellished sheath).

Reconstruction of women BOULG2' clothing. Jewelry (earrings, rings, torque), apron of bride's belt and beaded sheath of knife

Name: Celysse - (CELY)

Location: Vilyuy (Uluus: Nurbinsky)

GPS: 63.611233°N 118.73050°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, squared half-trunk coffin (external), thin wood board coffin (internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): snaffle bit, food offering (meat), bow, quiver and arrows (9), short sword, wooden spoon, tweezers, stitching awls (2), lighter, flint, pewter plate.

Individual: Male, 18-30 years old.

During the excavation, we recovered clothes. He rests on a blanket (fur and textile).

On the head: silk shroud, ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): coat, traditional Yakut belt, silk shirt.

On the hands: textile mittens.

On the lower limbs: nothing.

On the feet: boots (fragments).

Goods associated with the individual: signet rings (2).

Shaman status: no.

Wealth level: 2 (decorated belt, silk).

Signet rings, decorative elements and tweezers

Name: Haras - (HARA)

Localisation: Vilioui (Uluus: Nurbinsky)

GPS: 63.514050°N 118.779683°E

Period: 1700-1750 CE

Chest or coffin: medium wood board coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): thimble.

Individual: Immature (girl), 12-15 years old.

No clothing remains were found during the excavation.

Goods associated with the individual: earrings.

Shaman status: no.

The subject is a teenage girl. In Yakutia, individual graves of adolescent girls are extremely rare, and the ones we have are of shamans (Sordonokh, Kyss Ounouhoga) who wear so-called bride's belts.

Name: Ordiogone 1 - (ORDIO1)

Location: Viloui (Uluus: Nurbinsky)

GPS: 63.570467°N 119.184083°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, wooden logs coffin (external), tree trunk coffin (internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): saddle, stirrup, harness buckles, food offering (horse), remains of old horse (head and legs), leather purse, long sword, bow, quiver and arrows, bits, decorated sticks (2), birch pot, spoon, horse comb, whip (knout), pipe.

Individual: Male, elderly.

During the excavation, we recovered clothes. He rests on a white hare and textile blanket.

On the head: sable ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): textile coat, cotton shirt, belt.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: hide shorts, two pairs of thigh-high leg warmers (foal and hare), leather stockings.

On the feet: leather boots.

Shaman status: no.

Wealth level: 1 (horse coimb).

A pipe, knife and its sheath, wooden spoon, birch bowl and horse comb

Name: Oyogosse Tumula 3 - (OYO3)

Location: Vilyuy (Uluus: Nurbinsky)

GPS: 63.586739°N 119.129564°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, round log coffin (external), tree trunk coffin (internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): bow, headband, weapon, smoking kit.

Individual: Male (osteological sex), adult.

Only a belt was found during the excavation.

Shaman status: no.

Name: Ougout Kuel - (OUGT)

Location: Vilyuy (Uluus: Suntarsky)

GPS: 62.497000°N 117.59800°E

Period: 1,750 - 1,800 CE

Chest or coffin: squared half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): nothing.

Individual: Male, over 50 years old.

During the excavation, we recovered clothes.

On the head: fur shroud, fur ushanka, silk scarf.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): coat (sable and cotton), 2 leather garments, leather belt.

On the hands: leather mittens.

On the lower limbs: leather shorts, leather thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: sable socks, boots.

Shaman status: yes, (level 1: planted birch).

Name: Tungus Keul 4 - (TUNG4)

Location: Vilyuy (Uluus: Nurbinsky)

GPS: 63.597617°N 118.835517°E

Period: 1,750 - 1,800 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, wooden logs coffin (external), tree trunk coffin (internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): stirrups, food offering (horse), leather bag, dairy products, wooden bowl, spoon, knife and sheath, pipe.

Individual: Female, elderly.

During the excavation, we recovered clothes.

On the head: fur ushanka, silk scarf.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): pewter buttons (coat?).

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: nothing.

On the feet: textile socks, leather boots.

Goods associated with the individual: sun disc.

Shaman status: no.

Wealth level: 1 (horse comb).

Sun disk, birch bowl, wooden spoon and a knife

Name: Oulgoumda Berete 2 - (OULGB2)

Location: Vilyuy (Uluus: Suntarsky)

GPS: 62.006717°N 117.063217°E

Period: 1,800 - 1,922 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, squared half-trunk coffin (external), thin wood board coffin (internal)

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): not identified.

Individual: Male, over 30 years old.

The inside of the coffin was a single block of ice. The block was pierced to extract a piece of bone for DNA analysis. However, without any rapid method of defrosting and without damaging the remains, it was not possible to identify any items of clothing.

Shaman status: no.

Name: Oyogosse Tumula 2 - (OYO2A, OYO2C)

Location: Vilyuy (Uluus: Nurbinsky)

GPS: 63.587082°N 119.128899°E

Period: 1,800 - 1,922 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, wooden logs coffin (external), thin wood board coffin only for individual 2a (internal). The wooden logs coffin is divided in two with a coffin in the northern half containing individual 2a. The Southern half contains 2 individuals head to tail (2b and 2c) without coffins.

Number of individuals: 2 (3 in total)

Individual 2a: Female, 25-30 years old.

Placed in the northern part of the coffin. We recovered clothes during the excavations.

On the head: leather ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): textile clothing.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: nothing.

On the feet: nothing.

Goods associated with the individual: Yakute silver comb, brooch, porcelain pipe.

Shaman status: no.

Wealth level: 1 (silver comb).

Individu 2c: Immature, 7-8 years old.

No clothing was found during the excavation.

Shaman status: no.

Brooch, porcelaine pipe, silver comb

Name: Tchenkeloeïl - (TCHEN)

Location: Viloui (Uluus: Suntarsky)

GPS: 62.550217°N 117.440500°E

Period: 1,800 - 1,922 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, medium wood board coffin (external), thin wood board coffin (internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): nothing.

Individual: Immature (boy), 6-9 mois.

During the excavation, we recovered clothes.

On the head: fur ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): coat.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: nothing.

On the feet: nothing.

Goods associated with the individual: Christian cross.

Shaman status: no.

Verkhoyansk

Name: Byljasyk 3 - (BYLJ3)

Location: Doulgalaakh (Uluus: Verkhoyansky)

GPS: 66.882015°N 131.841671°E

Period: ~1,500 - 1,689 CE

Chest or coffin: half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): nothing.

Individual: Immature (boy), 11-12 years old.

We found a few rare items of clothing during the excavation. He rests on a leather blanket.

On the head: nothing.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): nothing.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts, thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: nothing.

Shaman status: no.

The subject, a child, lies on a smoked leather blanket. He presents a deliberate cranial deformation of the cradleboard type related to being tied to a board as a baby. This type of deformation is unknown among the Yakuts, but it is visible in some photos from the late 19th century among reindeer herder populations.

Name: Alyy - (ALYY)

Location: Boukhoulakh (Uluus: Verkhoyansky)

GPS: 67.144569°N 134.439299°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, half-rounders coffin (external) and squared half-trunk coffin (internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): knife, bronze cauldron with iron handle, wooden pot, food offering (horse), traditional Yakut sword, quiver containing arrows, bow, pipe, 2nd food offering (4 horse ribs).

Individual: Male, over 30 years old. He rests on a horse fur blanket. During the excavation, we recovered clothes.

On the head: sable shroud, sable ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): fur coat.

On the hands: fur pant.

On the lower limbs: fur thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: fur socks, leather boots.

Shaman status: no.

Wealth level: 1 (bronze and iron cauldron).

Reconstruction of man Alyy' clothing, pipe and knife

Bronze cauldron with iron handle, wooden pot, bow and arrows in leather sheath

Name: Atyyr Meite 1 - (ATYY1)

Location: Sartang (Uluus: Verkhoyansky)

GPS: 67.008786°N 133.012565°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): knife, wooden pot, food offering (foal), Yakut axe, Yakut cauldron (iron), quiver and arrows (7), bow and bow protection.

Individual: Male, over 30 years old.

During the excavation, we recovered clothes. He rests on a foal hide blanket.

On the head: ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): leather and fur coat, belt.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts, thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: boots.

Shaman status: no.

Wealth level: 4 (axe, decorated coat, belt with pearls, pearl embellished boots).

Reconstruction of man ATYY1' clothing, an axe and iron cauldron

Name: Bakhtakh 3 - (BAKHT3)

Location: Boukhoulakh (Uluus: Verkhoyansky)

GPS: 67.153475°N 134.522871°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, squared half-trunk coffin (external), tree trunk coffin (internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): bronze cauldron, food offerings (meat, horse rib, dairy product), leather bag, long sword, bow, quiver and arrows (7), wooden bowl, traditional Yakut vase (choron), knife.

Individual: Male, elderly with tuberculosis.

We recovered clothes during the excavations. He rests on a fur coat.

On the head: deer fur shroud, traditional Yakut ushanka (foal fur).

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): two fur coat, traditional Yakut belt, textile shirt.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: leather shorts, two pairs of thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: socks, boots.

Goods associated with the individual: signet ring.

Shaman status: no.

Wealth level: 2 (bronze cauldron, belt with metal decorations).

Reconstruction of man BAKHT3' clothing, sword, traditional Yakut monopod vase (choron), signet ring and repaired wooden bowl

Name: Ieralaakh - (IERA_A, IERA_B)

Location: Sartang (Uluus: Verkhoyansky)

GPS: 66.974615°N 132.923227°E

Period: 1,689-1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: squared half-trunk coffin, separated into two compartments: to the east, a young girl (A), to the west, a young boy (B).

Number of individuals: 2

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): pearls (2), to the east: wooden bowl, knife; to the west: Yakut monopod vase (choron).

Individual A: Young girl, 15-17 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations.

On the head: ushanka (below the head).

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): coat, beaded belt, shirt.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts, thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: boots.

Goods associated with the individual: torque, earrings (2).

Shaman status: yes, (level 2: restraint, bride's belt).

Wealth level: 2 (belt with pearls, torque).

Individual B: Young boy, 12-14 years old.

The clothes are poorly preserved.

On the head: foal hide (below the head).

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): coat.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: nothing.

On the feet: nothing.

Shaman status: no.

Reconstructions of young girl' clothing with its short and bride's belt and torque

Reconstructions of young girl' clothing. Traditional Yakut monopod vase (choron), wooden bowl, earrings and knife

Name: Kureleekh 1 - (KUR1)

Location: Boukhoulakh (Uluus: Verkhoyansky)

GPS: 67.148218°N 134.512504°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, round wood coffin (external), medium wood board coffin (internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): long sword, bow, wooden bark container, iron cauldron, other birch container, spoon, knife and case, quiver and arrows (7), whip (knout).

Individual: Male, young.

During the excavation, we recovered clothes. He rests on a coat.

On the head: fur shroud, traditional Yakut ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): fur coat.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts, thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: leather boots.

Goods associated with the individual: sun disk.

Shaman status: no.

Reconstructions of man KUR1' clothing, knife

Long sword, whip, birch bark pot, wooden container, iron cauldron and quiver and arrows

Name: Kureleekh 2 - (KUR2)

Location: Boukhoulakh (Uluus: Verkhoyansky)

GPS: 67.149374°N 134.507540°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, half-trunk coffin (external), squared half-trunk coffin (internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): bronze cauldron, food offering (meat), traditional Yakut vase (choron), knife, pair of scissors.

Individual: Female, elderly (over 60 years old).

During the excavation, we recovered clothes. She rests on a thin blanket.

On the head: fur ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): fur coat, bride's belt.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts, thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: boots.

Goods associated with the individual: sun disk, earrings (2), torque, signet ring, ring (2), bracelets (2).

Shaman status: yes (level 1: bride's belt).

Wealth level : 10 (bronze cauldron, decorated coat, belt with pearls, torque, 2 bracelets, 2 rings, knife with bronze decoration handle, lead object).

Reconstructions of woman KUR2' clothing, sun disk, earrings, rings and signet ring.

Bride's belt, bracelets, torque, bronze cauldron, pair of scissors and knife

Name: Tysarastaakh 2 - (TYSA2_A)

Location: Doulgalaakh (Uluus: Verkhoyansky)

GPS: 66.898597°N 131.838153°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, squared half-trunk coffin (external), squared half-trunk coffin (internal).

Number of individuals: 2

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): wooden bowl, food offering (horse), knife.

Individual 2a: Female, over 30 years old.

During the excavation, we recovered clothes.

On the head: sable ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): sable coat, beaded belt, coat, bride's belt.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: beaded shorts, horsehide thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: boots.

Goods associated with the individual: sun disk, torque (1), earrings (4).

Shaman status: yes (level 1: bride's belt).

Wealth level : 3 (decorated coat, belt with pearls, torque).

Individual 2b: Immature (boy), 4-6 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations. He is wrapped in a potentially leather cover.

On the head: ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): nothing.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts, thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: nothing.

Goods associated with the individual: sun disk.

Shaman status: no.

Reconstructions of woman Tysa2' clothing with sun disks

Reconstructions of woman *Tysa2'* clothing with jewelry (earrings, torque) and decorative elements of coat

Name: Buguyekh 3 - (BUGU3)

Location: Sartang (Uluus: Verkhoyansky)

GPS: 67.601103°N 133.524300°E

Period: 1,750 - 1,800 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, medium wood board coffin (external), tree trunk coffin (internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): wooden bowl with food offerings, knife and scabbard (leather).

Individual: Immature (boy), 15-17 years old.

During the excavation, we recovered clothes. He rests on a blanket.

On the head: ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): two leather coats, a leather belt.

On the hands: mittens.

On the lower limbs: shorts.

On the feet: boots.

Shaman status: no.

Buckle and birch bowl

Name: Kerdugen 1 - (KERDU)

Location: Boukhoulakh (Uluus: Verkhoyansky)

GPS: 67.173860°N 134.786084°E

Period: 1,750 - 1,800 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, squared half-trunk coffin (external and internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): knife and leather case, food offering (horse, dairy product), traditional Yakut vase (choron).

Individual: Male, young.

During the excavation, we recovered clothes. He rests on a leather blanket.

On the head: two traditional Yakut ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): fur coat, red textile coat, fur shirt, belt.

On the hands: mittens.

On the lower limbs: shorts, two pairs of thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: boots.

Goods associated with the individual: signet ring.

Shaman status: no.

Wealth level: 3 (red wool, belt with metal decorations, pearl embellished boots).

Reconstructions of man Kerdu' clothing with a decorated belt of metal elements, signet ring, traditional Yakut monopod vase (choron), knife and its leather sheath

Name: Kouranakh - (KOURA)

Location: Boukhoulakh (Uluus: Verkhoyansky)

GPS: 67.221015°N 132.162463°E

Period: 1,750 - 1,800 CE

Chest or coffin: anthropomorphic squared half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): wooden bowl, food offering (meat), pipe, lighter.

Individual: Immature (boy), 15-18 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations. He rests on a horsehide blanket.

On the head: fur shroud, traditional Yakut ushanka, sable boa.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): 2 fur coats, belt.

On the hands: mittens.

On the lower limbs: shorts, two pairs of thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: boots.

Goods associated with the individual: sun disk.

Shaman status: yes (level 3: hidden solar disk, sable band, longhair).

A sun disk, wooden bowl, lighter and pipe

Name: Lepsëi 1 - (LEPS1)

Location: Boukhoulakh (Uluus: Verkhoyansky)

GPS: 67.225726°N 132.157209°E

Period: 1,750 - 1,800 CE

Chest or coffin: squared half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): nothing.

Individual: Female, elderly.

No traces of clothing were found during the excavation.

Shaman status: no.

Name: Lepsei 2 - (LEPS2)

Location: Boukhoulakh (Uluus: Verkhoyansky)

GPS: 67.226741°N 132.162229°E

Period: 1,750 - 1,800 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, squared half-trunk coffin (external and internal).

Associated individual: a newborn was placed in the chest, along the female's left leg, and another on the outside of the chest (north wall of the chest).

Individual: Female, about 25 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations. She rests on a horsehide blanket.

On the head: sable ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): 2 coats, vaginal swab.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: fur thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: nothing.

Goods associated with the individual: torque, earrings (4).

Shaman status: no.

Wealth level: 1 (torque).

Jewelry: a torque with metal earrings

Name: Sordonokh - (SORD)

Localisation: Verkhoïansk (Uluus: Boukhoulakh)

GPS: 67.155580°N 132.076802°E

Period: 1750-1800 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, wooden logs coffin (external), squared half-trunk coffin (internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): wooden pot, spoon, birch bark container, traditional Yakut monopod vase, food offering

Individual: Female, 16-18 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations. She is covered and rests on a fur blanket (sable and horse).

On the head: sable fur shroud, traditional Yakut ushanka (sable), sable boa.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): sable fur coat, beaded belt, red textile coat, textile shirt, bride's belt.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: beaded shorts, fur thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: fur socks, leather boots.

Goods associated with the individual: earrings (2), torques (2), bracelets (2), sun disk.

Her grave was locally known as that of a shaman.

Shaman status: yes (level 2: hidden solar disk, bride's belt) her grave was locally known as that of as shaman.

Wealth level: 7 (decorated coat, red wool, belt with pearls, 2 torques, 2 bracelets).

Reconstructions of girl SORD' clothing, with sun disk and torque

Reconstructions of girl SORD' clothing, with a birch bark pot, traditional Yakut monopod vase (choron), wooden spoon and jewelry (earrings, bracelet and second torque)

Name: Byljasyk 2 - (BYLJ2)

Location: Doulgalaakh (Uluus: Verkhoyansky)

GPS: 66.884325°N 131.851161°E

Period: 1,800 - 1,922 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, half-rounders coffin (external), squared half-trunk coffin (internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): wooden bowl, taper used.

Individual: Male, 25-30 years old.

We recovered clothes during the excavations.

On the head: textile shroud, typical Russian ushanka, leather mask, fur ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): coat, shirt.

On the hands: mittens (unworn).

On the lower limbs: shorts, thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: boots.

Shaman status: unsure.

Reconstructions of man BYLJ2' clothing

Name: Khoumakhtaakh - (KHOUM)

Location: Batagay (Uluus: Verkhoyansky)

GPS: 67.544171°N 134.512024°E

Period: 1,800 - 1,922 CE

Individual: newborn (girl) ?

Name: Kuskhegir 2 - (KUSKG2)

Location: Stolby (Uluus: Verkhoyansky)

GPS: 67.527970°N 134.005518°E

Period: 1,800 - 1,922 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, squared half-trunk coffin (external and internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): nothing.

Individual: Male (osteological sex), 40-60 years old.

We recovered clothes. A shroud covers the entire body.

On the head: shroud (ushanka), silk scarf, traditional Yakut ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): green textile coat, blue textile jacket, textile shirt.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: nothing.

On the feet: socks, boots.

Goods associated with the individual: Christian cross.

Shaman status: no.

Name: Lepsëi 3 - (LEPS3)

Location: Boukhoulakh (Uluus: Verkhoyansky)

GPS: 62.227833°N 132.168570°E

Period: 1,800 - 1,922 CE

Chest or coffin: squared half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): nothing.

Individual: Male (osteological sex), adult.

We recovered clothes.

On the head: nothing.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): scarf tied at the wrist, coat.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: boots.

Shaman status: no.

Name: Myran 1 - (MYRAN)

Location: Boukhoulakh (Uluus: Verkhoyansky)

GPS: 67.218493°N 132.114809°E

Period: 1,800 - 1,922 CE

Chest or coffin: squared half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): knife, pearls.

Individual: Female, elderly.

We recovered clothes during the excavations.

On the head: fur ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): leather and blue textile clothes.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: boots.

Goods associated with the individual: Christian cross.

Shaman status: unsure.

Christian cross and bent blade of knife

Name: Ous Sire 1 - (OUS1)

Location: Doulgalaakh (Uluus: Verkhoyansky)

GPS: 66.850715°N 131.753359°E

Period: 1,800 - 1,922 CE

Chest or coffin: squared half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): pipe.

Individual: Male (osteological sex), young. During the excavations we recovered clothes.

On the head: textile shroud, traditional Yakut ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): deer coat.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts, thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: leather boots.

Goods associated with the individual: Christian cross.

Shaman status: unsure (level 1: long hair).

Indigirka

Name: Ebuguey 1 - (EBU1)

Location: Indigirka (Uluus: Oïmiakon)

GPS: 63.410198°N 143.037629°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: squared half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): knife with beaded case, food offering (horse).

Individual: Female, over 30 years old.

We recovered clothes.

On the head: ushanka, boa.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): undefined clothing.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts, thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: nothing.

Goods associated with the individual: torque, earrings (2), sun disk.

Shaman status: no.

Wealth level: 2 (pearl embellished sheath, torque).

Jewelry (earrings and torque) and decorative elements of clothing

Name: Ebuguey 2 - (EBU2)

Location: Indigirka (Uluus: Oïmiakon)

GPS: 63.417315°N 142.986493°E

Period: ~1,500 - 1,689 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, half-rounders coffin (external), medium wood board coffin (internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): horsehair braid, Yakut iron cauldron, food offering (meat), bowstring, archer's armband, whip (knout), quiver and arrows (7), snaffle bit, short sword, bow, knife.

Individual: Male, 25-35 years old.

We recovered clothes.

On the head: traditional Yakut ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): coat, belt buckle.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts.

On the feet: nothing.

Shaman status: no.

Wealth level: 1 (decorated coat).

An iron cauldron, iron fastener, snaffle bit and short sword

Name: Sobolokh 1 - (SOB1)

Location: Indigirka (Uluus: Oïmiakon)

GPS: 63.428150°N 142.950966°E

Period: 1,689 - 1,750 CE

Chest or coffin: half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): nothing.

Individual: Female, over 30 years old.

We recovered clothes. They were put on upside down and in reverse order (coat in contact with the body).

On the head: traditional Yakut ushanka (fur).

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): horsehide coat, leather dress.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: leather shorts, hide thigh-high leg warmers, hide stockings.

On the feet: leather boots.

Goods associated with the individual: earrings (2).

Shaman status: yes (level 1: clothing in reverse order).

Wealth level: 1 (decorated coat).

Reconstructions of woman SOB1' clothing with earrings and decorative elements of leather shorts

Reconstructions of woman SOB1' clothing with buttons (bead and metal) and decorative elements of coat

Name: Balagannakh 2 - (BALA2)

Location: Indigirka (Uluus: Oïmiakon)

GPS: 63.28064°N 143.40828°E

Period: 1,800 - 1,922 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, wooden logs coffin (external), thin wood board coffin (internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): oiled canvas.

Individual: Immature (girl), newborn. He is wrapped in a cotton and decorated textile (dark blue with white, green and pink dew flowers) scarf.

Goods associated with the individual: sun disk.

Shaman status: yes (level 2: planted birch, hidden sun disk).

A sun disk

Name: Balagannakh 3 - (BALA3)

Location: Indigirka (Uluus: Oïmiakon)

GPS: 63.291825°N 143.408048°E

Period: 1,800 - 1,922 CE

Chest or coffin: half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): nothing.

Individual: Male (osteological sex), 30-35 years old. We recovered clothes.

On the head: ushanka.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): leather coat, cotton shirt.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts, thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: boots.

Goods associated with the individual: Christian cross.

Shaman status: no.

Name: Omouk 1 - (OMK1)

Location: Indigirka (Uluus: Oïmiakon)

GPS: 64.148154°N 141.985612°E

Period: 1,800 - 1,922 CE

Chest or coffin: anthropomorphic squared half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): iron plate, food offering (dairy product), porcelain cup and saucer, ceramic teapot, fish skin bag, bone comb, lighter and fire bag, knife (Yakut), pipe, tobacco bag.

Individual: Female, over 30 years old.

We recovered clothes. She is covered in a cotton shroud.

On the head: Evene type ushanka, green silk scarf.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): festive apron with Evene design, beige velvet garment, fine leather coat, silk dress.

On the hands: traditional evenk hand guard.

On the lower limbs: nothing.

On the feet: deer thigh-high boots.

Goods associated with the individual: earrings (2), Christian cross, taper (2).

Shaman status: no.

Wealth level: 2 (ceramic teapot, silk dress).

Reconstructions of woman OMK1' clothing with traditional even hand guard

Three graves located a short distance from each other are on a promontory known in the region as Omouk, which translates to “the foreigner.” I.A. Khoudiakov wrote in 1865 that alongside the Yakuts lived those whom they referred to as the northern minority peoples, reindeer herders, known as Tungus (Evenks and Evene) or Omouk by the Yakuts, and self-identified as Lamuts. The promontory overlooks a marsh near an ancient road, and a bridge no longer exists. Two graves (including Omouk 1) are side by side, while a third (Omouk 3) is 140 meters to the northeast of the first two. A distinctive feature of Omouk 1 is its unique grave goods and burial practices, unparalleled among all excavated graves. Indeed, besides imported items associated with tea ceremonies and, based on the analysis of metabolites found in its hair, significant consumption of this beverage; beneath its head lies a cap made of leather and fabric, in the Even style, and a ceremonial apron, also of Evene style and patterns. It wears a silk scarf over its head, and its hairstyle, consisting of two braids, remains intact (contrary to common practice). Beneath the feet is a small fish skin bag, not Yakut, a bone comb decorated with geometric patterns, a lighter, a fire bag, and Even-style hand protectors. Omouk 1 is similar to the woman in Omouk 3, who possesses the same cross (a rarity as crosses greatly varies) and does not have her hair undone.

Reconstructions of woman OMKI' clothing with bone comb, Christian cross, pipe, tobacco bag, porcelain cup and saucer, ceramic teapot

Name: Omouk 3 - (OMK3)

Location: Indigirka (Uluus: Oïmiakon)

GPS: 64.148702°N 141.988118°E

Period: 1,800 - 1,922 CE

Chest or coffin: anthropomorphic thin wood board coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): nothing.

Individual: Female, 20-30 years old.

We recovered clothes.

On the head: red cotton scarf (shroud).

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): leather coat, dark blue silk shirt.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: shorts, leather thigh-high leg warmers.

On the feet: boots.

Goods associated with the individual: Christian cross, taper (1).

Shaman status: unsure.

Wealth level: 1 (silk shirt).

Christian cross and taper in the right hand

Name: Pokos (POK1)

Location: Indigirka (Uluus: Oïmiakon)

GPS: 63.340617°N 141.850282°E

Period: 1,800 - 1,922 CE

Chest or coffin: double chest, wooden logs coffin (external), thin wood board coffin with cephalic compartment (internal).

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): nothing.

Individual: Immature, 2-4 years old. He is buried in a cloth garment.

Goods associated with the individual: Christian cross.

Shaman status: no.

Name: Sobolokh 2 - (SOB2)

Location: Indigirka (Uluus: Oïmiakon)

GPS: 63.404700°N 142.886483°E

Period: 1,800 - 1,922 CE

Chest or coffin: thin wood board coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): nothing.

Individual: Immature (boy), 2-5 mois.

He is wrapped in two shrouds, one made of cotton with blue motifs and the other of paper.

A fragment of an icon envelops the lower limbs.

Shaman status: no.

Icon fragment around the legs

Name: Tomtor 2 - (TOMT2)

Location: Indigirka (Uluus: Oïmiakon)

GPS: 63.260228°N 143.137457°E

Period: 1,800 - 1,922 CE

Chest or coffin: squared half-trunk coffin.

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): pipe.

Individual: Male (osteological sex), young.

We recovered clothes.

On the head: shroud (scarf), scarf around the neck.

On the body (trunk and upper limbs): leather coat, shirt.

On the hands: nothing.

On the lower limbs: leather shorts.

On the feet: leather boots.

Goods associated with the individual: Christian cross.

Shaman status: no.

Name: Touora Urekh - (TOUO2, TOUO3)

Location: Indigirka (Uluus: Oïmiakon)

GPS: 63.61636°N 142.48616°E

Period: 1,800 - 1,922 CE

Number of individuals: 2

Associated goods (in the chest or on the chest): the remains of an exterior cross were found for individual 3 (Touora Urekh 3).

Chest or coffin: thin wood board coffin.

Individual 2: Immature, newborn (0-8 months).

The clothes were not retrieved.

Shaman status: no.

Chest or coffin: double chest, medium wood board coffin (external), thin wood board coffin (internal).

Individual 3: Immature, newborn (0-3 months). He is wrapped in a cotton shroud.

Shaman status: no.

Name: Tungus

Location: Buryatia

GPS: 53.598563°N 109.694591°E

Individual: male, adult.

Researchers inadvertently discovered this grave in the Barguzin Valley in Buryatia. Its general presentation and the grave goods are similar to those found in the tomb of Oulakh 4 located in the Lena Valley and dated to the 17th century, characterized notably by the absence of imported objects, garments made of leather, a bow, a knife, a knout, and a saddle placed on the legs. Except for Ebuguey1 we never found a knout in a tomb from Stage 1, and when a saddle is present, it is consistently placed under the head in the early phase, except in these two instances. Furthermore, the subject features a decorative element similar to Oulakh 4 and Boyola in central Yakutia.

Shaman status: no.

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